

Symmetries of a nondepolarizing optical medium and obtainment of anisotropy parameters by one or two Stokes vector measurements

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Abstract

It is shown that if a nondepolarizing optical medium has one or two symmetries the remaining nonzero anisotropy parameters can be obtained from the results of one or two stokes vector measurements without calculating the elements of the Mueller matrix.

Introduction

Optical properties of a nondepolarizing medium can be parametrized by four complex parameters. We can write these dimensionless parameters as the components of a vector \mathbf{h} [1,3]:

$$\mathbf{h} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau \\ \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

τ, α, β and γ are generally complex numbers but τ can always be chosen as real and positive if the overall phase is not taken into account. The other three parameters are associated with the complex anisotropy parameters of the optical medium. In terms of spectroscopic parameters, isotropic phase retardation (η), isotropic amplitude absorption (κ), circular dichroism (CD), circular birefringence (CB), horizontal and 45° linear dichorism (LD and LD'), horizontal and 45° linear birefringence (LB and LB'), τ, α, β and γ can be written as:

$$\tau = e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad \alpha = -e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iL}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\beta = -e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iL'}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad \gamma = e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iC}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

where $\chi = \eta - i\kappa$, $L = LB - iLD$, $L' = LB' - iLD'$, $C = CB - iCD$, $T = \sqrt{L^2 + L'^2 + C^2}$ [1,2].

It can be also shown that the \mathbf{h} vector is closely related to a 4×4 matrix, \mathbf{Z} , which is also defined in terms of the parameters τ, α, β and γ [1,4]:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau & \alpha & \beta & \gamma \\ \alpha & \tau & -i\gamma & i\beta \\ \beta & i\gamma & \tau & -i\alpha \\ \gamma & -i\beta & i\alpha & \tau \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

\mathbf{Z} matrix is a 4×4 analogue of the Jones matrix. In terms of \mathbf{Z} matrices Mueller-Jones matrix of a nondepolarizing optical medium can be written as:

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{Z}^*\mathbf{Z}. \quad (5)$$

Eq.(5) leads to an expression for the Mueller-Jones matrix in terms of the parameters τ, α, β and γ :

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^*}{\beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^*} & \frac{\tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^*}{+i(\gamma\beta^* - \beta\gamma^*)} & \frac{\tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^*}{+i(\alpha\gamma^* - \gamma\alpha^*)} & \frac{\tau\gamma^* + \gamma\tau^*}{+i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*)} \\ \frac{\tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^*}{-i(\gamma\beta^* - \beta\gamma^*)} & \frac{\tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^*}{-\beta\beta^* - \gamma\gamma^*} & \frac{\alpha\beta^* + \beta\alpha^*}{+i(\tau\gamma^* - \gamma\tau^*)} & \frac{\alpha\gamma^* + \gamma\alpha^*}{+i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*)} \\ \frac{\tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^*}{-i(\alpha\gamma^* - \gamma\alpha^*)} & \frac{\alpha\beta^* + \beta\alpha^*}{-i(\tau\gamma^* - \gamma\tau^*)} & \frac{\tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^*}{+\beta\beta^* - \gamma\gamma^*} & \frac{\beta\gamma^* + \gamma\beta^*}{+i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*)} \\ \frac{\tau\gamma^* + \gamma\tau^*}{-i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*)} & \frac{\alpha\gamma^* + \gamma\alpha^*}{-i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*)} & \frac{\beta\gamma^* + \gamma\beta^*}{-i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*)} & \frac{\tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^*}{-\beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^*} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

This form of the Mueller matrix provides an interface between complex theoretical anisotropy parameters and directly measurable real Stokes parameters via the equation $\mathbf{M}\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S}'$ where \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{S}' are the input and output Stokes vectors of complete polarization states of light. Eq.6 can be also obtained from the Jones matrix as described in the Appendix.

Symmetries of the optical medium

If one of the anisotropy parameters is zero the optical medium has a symmetry. For example, if $\gamma = 0$ there is no circular anisotropy and the optical medium can be characterized by five real parameters: one for τ and two real parameters for each one of α and β . In some cases we may have two symmetries:

$$\alpha \neq 0, \beta = 0, \gamma = 0, \quad (7)$$

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As special cases, we may have optical media with α, β, γ being all pure real or pure imaginary numbers. Pure real case corresponds to a Hermitian \mathbf{Z} matrix that describes a general diattenuator and pure imaginary anisotropy parameters correspond to a unitary \mathbf{Z} matrix that describes a general retarder.

Obtainment of anisotropy parameters by one or two Stokes vector measurements

Under some symmetry conditions we can obtain the anisotropy parameters of a nondepolarizing medium without calculating the elements of the Mueller matrix. We can find the

nonzero parameters directly from the measured output Stokes vectors corresponding to one or two inputs of complete polarization states of light. For example, let us assume that the optical medium under investigation has no circular anisotropy ($\gamma = 0$). The associated Mueller matrix reduces to

$$\mathbf{M} = \left(\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* & \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* & \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* & i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) \\ \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* & \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* - \beta\beta^* & \alpha\beta^* + \beta\alpha^* & i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*) \\ \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* & \alpha\beta^* + \beta\alpha^* & \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* & i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) \\ \hline -i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) & -i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*) & -i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) & \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* - \beta\beta^* \end{array} \right). \quad (8)$$

We can obtain τ, α and β up to an arbitrary phase by two Stokes vector measurements without calculating the elements of the Mueller matrix. Suppose that we measure the output Stokes vectors that correspond to right and left handed circular polarization states of input light. According to Eq.8

$$\mathbf{M}\mathbf{S}_R = \mathbf{S}'_R \rightarrow \mathbf{M} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* + i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) \\ \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* + i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*) \\ \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* + i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) \\ -i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) + \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* - \beta\beta^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} S'_{R0} \\ S'_{R1} \\ S'_{R2} \\ S'_{R3} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{M}\mathbf{S}_L = \mathbf{S}'_L \rightarrow \mathbf{M} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* - i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) \\ \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* - i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*) \\ \tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^* - i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) \\ -i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*) - \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} S'_{L0} \\ S'_{L1} \\ S'_{L2} \\ S'_{L3} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{S}_R and \mathbf{S}_L are the input Stokes vectors corresponding to the right and left handed circular polarization states and \mathbf{S}'_R and \mathbf{S}'_L are the output Stokes vectors corresponding to these inputs. Eqs.9 and 10 can be solved for τ, α and β up to an arbitrary phase by assuming that τ is real and positive:

$$\tau = \sqrt{\frac{S'_{R0} + S'_{R3}}{2}} = \sqrt{\frac{S'_{L0} - S'_{L3}}{2}} \quad (11)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{4\tau} (S'_{R1} + S'_{L1} + i(S'_{R2} - S'_{L2})) \quad (12)$$

$$\beta = \frac{1}{4\tau} (S'_{R2} + S'_{L2} + i(S'_{L1} - S'_{R1})) \quad (13)$$

Similarly, we can find the nonzero parameters of optical media with $\alpha = 0$ or $\beta = 0$. If there is only one nonzero anisotropy, the parameters can be found by means of a single Stokes vector measurement. For example, if $\alpha \neq 0, \beta = 0$ and $\gamma = 0$ the Mueller matrix given in Eq.6 reduces to

$$\mathbf{M} = \left(\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* & \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* & 0 & 0 \\ \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* & \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* & i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) \\ 0 & 0 & -i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) & \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* \end{array} \right). \quad (14)$$

Nonzero parameters can be solved in many ways by a single Stokes vector measurement. For example, with an input light of 45° linear polarization

$$\mathbf{M}\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S}' \rightarrow \mathbf{M} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^* \\ \tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^* \\ \tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^* \\ -i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} S'_0 \\ S'_1 \\ S'_2 \\ S'_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Eq.15 can be solved for τ and α up to an arbitrary phase by assuming that τ is real and positive

$$\tau = \sqrt{\frac{S'_0 + S'_2}{2}} \quad (16)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{2\tau} (S'_1 - iS'_3) \quad (17)$$

Special cases: Hermitian and unitary \mathbf{Z} matrices

In some special cases we can obtain the anisotropy parameters in terms of more concrete properties of the medium. If τ, α, β and γ are pure real numbers \mathbf{Z} matrix is a Hermitian matrix and it generates a general diattenuator Mueller matrix. If we also assume that $\gamma = 0$ the \mathbf{Z} matrix generates a linear diattenuator Mueller matrix:

$$\mathbf{M} = \left(\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} \tau^2 + \alpha^2 + \beta^2 & 2\tau\alpha & 2\tau\beta & 0 \\ \hline 2\tau\alpha & \tau^2 + \alpha^2 - \beta^2 & 2\alpha\beta & 0 \\ \hline 2\tau\beta & 2\alpha\beta & \tau^2 - \alpha^2 + \beta^2 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau^2 - \alpha^2 - \beta^2 \end{array} \right). \quad (18)$$

where τ, α , and β are real numbers. On the other hand, a matrix of a linear diattenuator with an axis at an angle θ and intensity transmittances q, r is given as [5]

$$\mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} q+r & (q-r)\cos(2\theta) & (q-r)\sin(2\theta) & 0 \\ \hline (q-r)\cos(2\theta) & (q+r)\cos^2(2\theta) + 2\sqrt{qr}\sin^2(2\theta) & (q+r-2\sqrt{qr})\sin(2\theta)\cos(2\theta) & 0 \\ \hline (q-r)\sin(2\theta) & (q+r-2\sqrt{qr})\sin(2\theta)\cos(2\theta) & (q+r)\sin^2(2\theta) + 2\sqrt{qr}\cos^2(2\theta) & 0 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 0 & 2\sqrt{qr} \end{array} \right). \quad (19)$$

Comparing the matrices given in Eq.18 and Eq.19 we obtain

$$\tau = \frac{\sqrt{q} + \sqrt{r}}{2}, \quad \alpha = \frac{(\sqrt{q} - \sqrt{r})\cos(2\theta)}{2}, \quad \beta = \frac{(\sqrt{q} - \sqrt{r})\sin(2\theta)}{2} \quad (20)$$

If τ is real but α, β and γ are pure imaginary numbers then the \mathbf{Z} matrix is a unitary matrix and it generates a Mueller matrix of a general retarder. If we also assume that $\gamma = 0$ the Mueller matrix reduces to a linear retarder matrix

$$\mathbf{M} = \left(\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} \tau^2 + \alpha^2 + \beta^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & \tau^2 + \alpha^2 - \beta^2 & 2\alpha\beta & -2\tau\beta \\ \hline 0 & 2\alpha\beta & \tau^2 - \alpha^2 + \beta^2 & 2\tau\alpha \\ \hline 0 & 2\tau\beta & -2\tau\alpha & \tau^2 - \alpha^2 - \beta^2 \end{array} \right). \quad (21)$$

A linear retarder with a fast axis at an angle θ and retardance δ can also be written as [5]

$$\mathbf{M} = \left(\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & \cos^2(2\theta) + \sin^2(2\theta)\cos(\delta) & \sin(2\theta)\cos(2\theta)(1 - \cos(\delta)) & -\sin(2\theta)\sin(\delta) \\ \hline 0 & \sin(2\theta)\cos(2\theta)(1 - \cos(\delta)) & \sin^2(2\theta) + \cos^2(2\theta)\cos(\delta) & \cos(2\theta)\sin(\delta) \\ \hline 0 & \sin(2\theta)\sin(\delta) & -\cos(2\theta)\sin(\delta) & \cos(\delta) \end{array} \right). \quad (22)$$

Comparing the matrices given in Eq.21 and Eq.22 we obtain

$$\tau = \cos\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right), \quad \alpha = \cos(2\theta)\sin\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right), \quad \beta = \sin(2\theta)\sin\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right) \quad (23)$$

Appendix

We can obtain Eq.6 from the Jones matrix by using the well known relation $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{J} \otimes \mathbf{J}^*)\mathbf{A}^\dagger = \mathbf{M}$. In order to show this we first write the Jones matrix in the Pauli basis:

$$\mathbf{J} = \tau\sigma_0 + \alpha\sigma_1 + \beta\sigma_2 + \gamma\sigma_3 \quad (24)$$

where

$$\sigma_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

Then we observe that

$$\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{J} \otimes \sigma_0)\mathbf{A}^\dagger, \quad \mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{A}(\sigma_0 \otimes \mathbf{J}^*)\mathbf{A}^\dagger \quad (26)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i & -i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{A}^\dagger = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & i \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (27)$$

Now, it is straightforward to show that

$$\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{J} \otimes \mathbf{J}^*)\mathbf{A}^\dagger = \mathbf{M}. \quad (28)$$

References

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